

Scalar Potentials Compatible with a Decoupled Dirac Hypergeometric Equation

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In a previous note (1), it was shown one may write the two solutions of the one dimensional Dirac equation with a scalar potential as $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$ and $v(x)=v_0(x)v_1(x)$ where $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ are ground state solutions. One may then obtain two new differential equations for $v_1(x)$ and $u_1(x)$ with the scalar potential removed, but u_0 and v_0 present. These two may then be decoupled. The equation for $v_1(x)$ is of the form of a Hermite DE for the scalar potential $g|x|$ if one obtains solutions for $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ by inspection. In this note, we wish to find more general potentials which are compatible with a decoupled DE for $v_1(x)$ as a hypergeometric equation. In addition, we do not wish to find solutions for $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ by inspection. Instead, the decoupled DE is written in terms of $f(x)=v_0(x)/u_0(x)$. This in turn is shown to be related to the scalar potential $V(x)$ through $f(x)=(C_2+V(x))/(C_3+V(x))$. Thus, by insisting the decoupled DE for $v_1(x)$ be of a hypergeometric form, one may determine $V(x)$ forms which are compatible. (Similar arguments should hold for $u_1(x)$.) We first show $V(x)=a+bx$ is an acceptable form, but then, using transformations argue that $V(x)= [a \exp(-ax) + b] / b \exp(-ax)$ is another form leading to a Rodrigues polynomial solution.

Decoupled Dirac Equation

We start with the one dimensional Dirac equations with a scalar potential $V(x)$ as given in (2):

$$-d/dx v(x) = (E - m_0 - V(x)) u(x) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx u(x) = (E + m_0 + V(x)) v(x) \quad ((1))$$

We may use $v(x)=v_0(x)v_1(x)$ and $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$ (where $v_0(x)$ and $u_0(x)$ are ground state solutions) to obtain a decoupled equation for $v_1(x)$. (A similar decoupled equation should exist for $u_1(x)$.) Details are given in (1). The results are:

$$u_1 = [-v_0 d/dx v_1 + E_0 v_1 u_0] / (E u_0) \quad ((2a))$$

$$d/dx u_1 = [-1/(E^* E^* u_0^* u_0)] [E d/dx u_0] [-v_0 d/dx v_1 + E_0 v_1 v_0] + [1/(E u_0)] [-v_0 d/dx d/dx v_1 - d/dx v_1 d/dx v_0 + E_0 u_0 d/dx v_1 + E_0 v_1 d/dx u_0] \quad ((2b))$$

and

$$u_0 d/dx u_1 + E_0 u_1 v_0 = E v_1 v_0 \quad ((3))$$

Inserting ((2a)) and ((2b)) into ((3)) yields a second order DE for $v_1(x)$ with the following coefficients:

$$[\text{Coefficient of } d/dx d/dx v_1] \quad -v_0/E \quad ((4a))$$

$$[\text{Coefficient of } d/dx v_1] \left(\frac{v_0}{E} \frac{d/dx u_0}{u_0} + \frac{1}{E} \left[-\frac{d/dx v_0}{v_0} + E_0 \frac{u_0}{v_0} \right] + E_0 \frac{v_0(-v_0)}{(E u_0)} \right) \quad ((4b))$$

$$[\text{Coefficient of } v_1] \frac{v_0(-E+E_0)}{E} + \frac{-1}{E} \left(\frac{d/dx u_0}{u_0} \right) E_0 \frac{v_0}{v_0} + \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right) \left(\frac{d/dx u_0}{u_0} \right) \quad ((4c))$$

In general, $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$, ground state solutions of the Dirac equations ((1)) may be complicated functions. In this note, we wish to consider the coefficients ((4)) such that the second order DE for $v_1(x)$ is of a hypergeometric form. First, however, we consider the case of a Hermite DE because it was shown in (1) that $V(x)=g|x|$ yields such a result.

As a first step we divide the equations ((4)) by $-v_0/E$. Then, the coefficient of $d/dx v_1(x)$ must be $2x$ and that of $v_1(x)$ a constant in order to have the Hermite DE. This yields:

$$[\text{Coefficient of } v_1(x)] \left(\frac{E_0-E}{E} + \text{constant} = C_1 = E_0 \frac{d/dx u_0}{u_0} - E_0 \frac{d/dx v_0}{v_0} \right)$$

One may use the Dirac equations ((1)) to write:

$$\frac{d/dx u_0}{v_0} = (E+m_0+V) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d/dx u_0}{u_0} = \frac{d/dx u_0}{v_0} \left(\frac{v_0}{u_0} \right) = \left(\frac{v_0}{u_0} \right) (E+m_0+V)$$

Or

$$C_1/E_0 = (E+m_0+V) \left[-1 + \left(\frac{v_0}{u_0} \right) \right] \quad \text{or} \quad C_2 = V(-1+v_0/u_0) - (E+m_0)(v_0/u_0)$$

If one denotes $v_0/u_0=f(x)$, there follows the relationship:

$$C_2 = V(x)(-1+f(x)) + C_3 f(x) \quad \text{or} \quad f(x) = \frac{C_2+V}{C_3+V} \quad ((5))$$

Consider next the coefficient of $d/dx v_1(x)$:

$$-\frac{d/dx u_0}{u_0} - \frac{d/dx v_0}{v_0} - E_0 \frac{E u_0}{v_0} + E_0/E \frac{v_0}{u_0} \quad ((6))$$

This should equate to $ax+b$ where a and b are unknown constants. Let $v_0/u_0=f(x)$. Then:

$$-(E+m_0+V) f(x) + \frac{1}{f(x)}(E-m_0-V) - E_0 E \left(\frac{1}{f(x)} \right) + E_0/E f(x) \quad ((7))$$

Using ((5)) one may express $f(x)$ in terms of $V(x)$. Thus, one has an equation in $V(x)$ which should equal $ax+b$. This should restrict the form of $V(x)$.

One finds:

$$x \text{ Order}(V(x)V(x)) = \text{Order}(V(x)V(x)V(x)) \quad ((8))$$

This suggests $V(x)$ is linear in x in order for the Hermite DE to exist. It has already been shown in (1) that an exact Hermite DE with a coefficient of 1 for $d/dx d/dx v_1$, $2x$ for $d/dx v_1$ and a constant coefficient for $v_1(x)$ exists.

Transformations

The Hermite DE is not the most general hypergeometric form. In (3) it is argued that:

$$p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) + \text{constant } v_1(x) = 0 \quad ((9))$$

where $p(x)$ is at most a quadratic in x and $q(x)$ linear is a general form which guarantees a Rodrigues polynomial solution. The original DE for v_1 contains $-v_0(x)/E$ as its coefficient, but $v_0(x)$ is unknown and most likely complicated, so it is divided out. Thus, one may introduce transformations $y=g(x)$ which yield a quadratic in y as the coefficient of $d/dy d/dy v_1(y)$ yet still impose a linear polynomial for the coefficient of $d/dy v_1(y)$. $v_1(y)$ remains a constant.

From results with the Hulthen potential, we suggest :

$$y = \exp(-qx) \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Then: } \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right) \frac{d}{dy} v_1 = -q y \frac{d}{dy} v_1(y)$$

The coefficient of $d/dy d/dy v_1(y)$ is quadratic and the coefficient of $d/dy v_1(y)$ must be linear so:

$$ay + b_1 = q^* q y \text{ (from the original } d/dx d/dx v_1) - q y \frac{d}{dy} \text{ (Original coefficient of } d/dx v_1)$$

The original coefficient, however, may be written in terms of $V(x)$ which can be written as $V(y)$. Thus:

$$(a + q^* q)y + b_1 = -qy \left[\frac{-(E + m_0 + V)}{(C_2 + V)} \frac{(C_2 + V)}{(C_3 + V)} + \frac{(C_3 + V)}{(C_2 + V)} \frac{(E - m_0 - V)}{(C_3 + V)} - E_0 \frac{E}{(C_3 + V)} \frac{(C_3 + V)}{(C_2 + V)} + \frac{E_0}{E} \frac{(C_3 + V)}{(C_2 + V)} \right] \quad ((11))$$

Consider dividing $-qy$ on the RHS of ((11)) and calling:

$$z = \frac{(a + q^* q)y + b_1}{(-qy)} \quad ((12)) \quad V(x) \text{ may be considered as } V(z)$$

Then:

$$\text{Order}(z) \text{ Order}(V(z)V(z)) = \text{Order}(V(z)V(z)V(z))$$

Thus, one may anticipate a solution of $V(z)$ linear in z i.e.:

$$V(z) = V(x) = a_2 z + b_2 = a_2 \left[\frac{(a + q^* q)y + b_1}{(-qy)} \right] + b_2 = a_2 \left[\frac{(a + q^* q)\exp(-qx) + b_1}{(-q\exp(-qx))} \right] + b_2$$

It seems that one may use a more general transformation, say $y = \exp(-qx) + d$. Then one would have $-q \exp(-qx) + d$ in the denominator.

The coefficient of $v_1(x)$ is already a constant because this criterion was used to obtain ((5)) in the first place.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems one may write $u(x) = u_0(x)u_1(x)$ and $v(x) = v_0(x)v_1(x)$ where $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ are ground state solutions of the one dimensional Dirac equations ((1)) with a scalar potential. $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ are more general solutions. This leads to two equations for $v_1(x)$ and $u_1(x)$ which may be decoupled. The decoupled DE for $v_1(x)$ is of the form of a second order linear DE. If one insists this match a hypergeometric equation, the coefficient of $v_1(x)$ must be a constant. This leads to the relationship:

$$f(x) = v_0(x)/u_0(x) = [C_2 + V(x)]/[C_3 + V(x)].$$

One may introduce a transformation $y = \exp(-qx)$. This yields a quadratic polynomial for the coefficient of $d/dy/dy v_1(y)$ (after it has been divided by $-v_0/E$). Thus, the coefficient of $d/dy v_1(y)$ must be a linear polynomial. This restriction seems to require:

$$V(x) = a_2[(a + q^2) \exp(-qx) + b_1]/(-q \exp(-qx) + b_2)$$

In order for $v_1(x)$ to have a Rodrigues polynomial solution. A more general transformation of $y = \exp(-qx) + d$ would yield $-q(\exp(-qx) + d)$ in the denominator of the expression for $V(x)$. Such a solution is only a possible solution, but there seems to be interest in the literature for solutions of this type.

References

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